

SCIENTIFIC WORLDWIDE - AS A VALUE**Boybekova Shahnoza Aliyevna***Qarshi State University*BoybekovaShahnoza86@gmail.com

Annotation: The article examines the processes related to the fact that scientific achievements are one of the main values and their influence on the formation of the worldview system.

Key Words: Values, spiritual heritage, democratic state, reform, development, humanity, intellect, science, material and spiritual life, civil society, way of thinking, scientific research.

Today, great progress is being made in the field of science in our country. The development and strengthening of the scientific worldview is of great importance in the worldview of young people. During this period, important changes are taking place in the structure of the society's value system. Science, scientific knowledge, and rationalism have priority in the system of moral values of the society.

It is known that cultural and spiritual values play an important role in society and human life. It includes scientific, technical and intellectual opportunities, education, training, medical services, national heritage, cultural masterpieces in various forms, language, literature, art, folk crafts, unique historical and cultural monuments, architecture and etc. are included. The fact that science is a value that eternalizes a person and encourages him to be good and creative is clearly expressed in the Holy Quran and Hadith, which are the holy books of Islam, and in the oral art of the wise people.

In the 21st century, the development of information technologies, the penetration of computers into all areas of human activity, has developed in the direction of the integration processes of scientific knowledge, the integration processes of two philosophical sciences and the integration processes of general

scientific knowledge. The change of the scientific landscape of the world, the emergence of the idea of the principle of "universal evolutionism" had a great impact on the processes of integration of scientific knowledge. The process of integration in scientific knowledge is understood in the sense of their synthesis, organic unity, rather than the mixing of one science or scientific knowledge. In this, the basic concepts in the knowledge system are transformed. Integration processes in scientific knowledge are the unification of concepts and categories of sciences; emergence of general scientific methods; penetration of methods of one science into other sciences; it is manifested in the form of the emergence of general research objects and complex sciences.

Therefore, at the basis of the modern integration processes in scientific knowledge, firstly, the internal laws of the development of scientific knowledge, and secondly, the development of information technologies, and this process will become stronger in the future. The main factor for this is the idea of global evolutionism. After all, imaginations about coevolutionary processes in all spheres of existence - nature, society, human culture, science, philosophy, etc., determination of the mechanisms of these processes, require closer interaction of natural and humanitarian knowledge. In addition, global problems facing humanity are also solved through the integration of scientific knowledge

In general, science is a spiritual-intellectual value that unites all the peoples of the earth and serves their common interests and goals. Because all the nations on Earth rely on different religious beliefs, different moral values and cultures, different artistic and aesthetic tastes, different political systems and ideologies, only scientific values bring peoples and countries closer to each other.

The fundamental reforms implemented in the field of science and education in our country are undoubtedly aimed at the full use of the potential of science in the rational solution of complex socio-economic problems, and the improvement of the scientific and intellectual potential of our people. In order to correctly form the spiritual and scientific views of the young generation, they will be enlightened

about the meaning of national identity, the essence of science, its components, its role and importance in human life, and instill in them high scientific, spiritual, religious standards and requirements. It is necessary to make a decision, to develop the thinking of society. The intellectual culture of a person can be formed on the basis of principles such as a new understanding of education, harmonizing the spiritual value of a person with his freedom, and humanizing education.

As a result, a new value system of education based on humanitarian principles will emerge. Therefore, the humanization of education ensures people's self-awareness in this world, and the main goal of humanization of education leads to the formation of a humanistic worldview, relevant knowledge and skills. It is the balance of human and intellectual qualities that are connected to each other that leads to the understanding of the process of education and knowledge at the level of valuable consciousness, to the correct understanding of the essence of science and scientific values.

Scientific values, as an important component of our spiritual values and a basic value, are distinguished by a number of their characteristics and laws of development. Understanding science as a value requires understanding that the great creative power of scientific knowledge and science in society and individual life is connected with the establishment of democratic values.

Scientific values - ideas, works, educational and scientific institutions that allow the realization of intellectual and spiritual abilities and talents in people, the in-depth study of the scientific heritage of our ancestors, the creation of innovations and discoveries through researching reality, a community of scientists, a complex of scholars. Scientific values are a comprehensive philosophical concept. This concept dialectically combines succession, traditionalism, and innovation in science. Among the scientific values, the immortal works of all our great scientists who left a deep mark on the history of mankind can be included. The advantage and superiority of scientific values over other values is that it provides reliable, empirically tested knowledge.

Educational and scientific institutions also make up the structure of scientific values. Educational institutions have a noble goal - to teach young people the basics of science, scientific innovations, to develop scientific thinking and creative abilities in young people. Consistent implementation of science, education, and vocational training is a wide opportunity for talented young people. Today, it is necessary for our youth to acquire deep knowledge and high potential, to find and form personnel capable of achieving their goals. The role and importance of the educational system in increasing the status of scientific values in the age of information technologies, as well as the ways of increasing the effectiveness of scientific values in the modern education process and the issues of the social responsibility of the scientist is to be studied.

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